

Original Research Article

Student's Perceptions Regarding Teaching Methodologies of Community Medicine Department, Ayub Medical College, Abbottabad

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Abstract

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Teaching strategies are the principles and methods that are instrumented by teachers to attain the required optimal learning by students, which depends not only on the subject that is supposed to be taught but also by the nature and psychology of learner. The appropriation and efficiency of a teaching method lies in its relation with the characteristics of learner and the main goal it has supposed to bring about. The study was carried out in Ayub medical college, Abbottabad from December 2016 to August 2017. The methods primarily employed in this research were In-depth interview (IDI) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Both FDGs and Interviews were conducted among fourth year MBBS students by team mates. The sampling technique that we used in this study was non-probability purposive sampling. In all about 8 FDGs and 4 in-depth interviews were conducted. Our study revealed that most of the students were not satisfied with one-way teaching. Teacher does not involve students in learning process. Most teachers are unaware of use of technology, which teachers referred to lack of trainings and seminars. In large class strength, every teacher can't adopt interactive method of teaching. Project writing and field visits were admired. Students were not satisfied with class tests schedule. With the new advancements in education system around the world, teaching methods are also constantly evolving. The conclusion of this study is that teaching is a multidimensional process, which involves key stakeholders that are the teachers, students, and the administration. For an effective teaching, all the stakeholders have to work optimally. These developments can be enhanced with student's feedback, because they are the direct people being affected from the various teaching methods used in a typical classroom of a medical college.

Keywords: Learning Environment Medical Education, Teaching Methods, Student's Behaviour

INTRODUCTION

A teacher is a person who gives knowledge or instructs other to learn and understand something (Smith, 2016).

Teaching strategies are the principles and methods that are instrumented by teachers to attain the required

optimal learning by students, which depends not only on the subject that is supposed to be taught but also by the nature and psychology of learner. The appropriation and efficiency of a teaching method lies in its relation with the characteristics of learner and the main goal it has supposed to bring about (Peter, 2008).

There are number of teaching approaches, but they are mainly divided into teacher centered and student centered. In the first approach, the active stakeholder is the teacher whose main role is to pass knowledge and information onto his students via lectures or direct instructions. While the students receive that information passively. In this type of teaching approach students learning and assessment is established through various objectively structured tests and exams. The second approach is student centered while teacher is an authorized entity in this model, teachers and students play an equally active role in the process of learning. The main role of teacher in this model is to facilitate and coach the student learning with interactive involvement of students and overall comprehension of material. The student assessment is done formally and informally through assignments, group's projects, student's portfolios and student active participation in the learning process (Teaching methods, 2017).

Many people feel that the 'old' methods have worked for years, so there is no need to change. Others feel that student-centered methods of teaching where the responsibility is on the student to learn are not viable because the students are not well-prepared. These people forget that when a teacher teaches, there is no guarantee that the student learns (Amin and Hoon, 2004).

During the Greek world, professional experience was more important than books in medical education. Books were used as adjuncts which never took the place of practical knowledge (John, 1953). The progress in the art and science of medical teaching and learning of what so called medical education has been very outstanding. Keeping the various forms of learning and curriculum the mainstreams of pedagogical principles, teaching and learning has been more scientific and clear, which have made us capable to solve a problem rather than only identifying them (Amin and Hoon, 2004).

Perception is what people think about others when they come in an interaction. This interaction is determine by what other thinks, feels and their liking to behave towards materials and ideas accordingly. Perception of a student about teaching methods in learning process is important and it effects a teacher's teaching strategies in some way or the other. Because a good teacher has got affective, cognitive and psychomotor talents he/she would like to know about his/her learner's behavior and attitude toward learning (Adediwura and Tayo, ND). As student's involvement in learning process is very critical their perception results in methodological challenges for teachers. This perception of students is

important for teachers to review his teaching strategies and adopt an optimum teaching method to enhance student understanding of a particular subject. No subject can be learnt properly without communication, the use of its appropriate terms facilitates the understanding of whatever is being learnt (Ahmad, ND). The pillar of educational system lies on a core of devoted, knowledgeable, competent and well-trained teachers. A teacher who has high value on this scale in the perception of the students is likely to entertain confidence, respect and compliment of his students. Thus, the students' perception of the teaching

Literature Review

The most dominant form of teaching in the first half of twentieth century was teacher directed instruction. In every lesson, teachers tended to lecture and demonstrate first, then set their students related deskwork to do. No one questioned if the method was effective. In late 1950s, teachers were being encouraged to use a 'project approach' and to engage students in more group work. Some teachers resisted even these modest changes. But slowly over the next decade more innovative approaches did appear, with activity-based methods recommended in the primary years, and the use of new' medium of educational television and film (Damodharan and Rengarapan, 2017; Ingram and Nelson, 2008; Tapscott, 1998). The period of 1970s to 2000 was a sudden growth in educational research exploring the effects of different approaches to teaching. Simultaneously, research in the field of psychology was continuing its investigations into how humans learn – how they acquire knowledge, how they process information, how they develop skills and strategies, how they think and reason. A much less structured form of direct teaching – interactive whole-class teaching – has gained somewhat greater acceptance, particularly in the United Kingdom and some other countries (Shulman, 1987). Studies of teaching methods used in countries where students do extremely well in international surveys of achievement (e.g., Hungary and Japan) suggest that the teachers in those countries employ interactive whole-class teaching methods widely and effectively. Interactive whole-class teaching has been recommended in government guidelines in the United Kingdom as a possible means of raising students' attainment levels in basic literacy and numeracy (Tapscott, 1998).

The researchers suggest some of the methods can very well be applied by the modern teachers. As the researchers feel that basically the core objective of teaching should never be deviated by the use of an innovative method. These modern methods of teaching are discussed one by one (Damodharan and Rengarapan, 2017).

Discovery learning is a way of learning which requires

students to investigate a topic, issue or problem by active means, obtain pertinent information, interpret causes and effects where relevant, and arrive at conclusions or solutions. The method is particularly appropriate for achieving important objectives in social studies, science, geography, history, health, environmental education and mathematics (North Carolina Department of Instruction, 2017).

In discovery learning the teacher may provide all necessary resource materials but learners are given little or no direction for carrying out their investigations. They must decide for themselves the most appropriate method for tackling the investigation and must then reach their own conclusions from the observations they make. The teacher usually explains the lesson objectives to the students, provides initial input or explanation to help students begin the task efficiently. This method is generally regarded as a motivating method, enjoyed by learners (Ingram and Nelson, 2008; North Carolina Department of Instruction, 2017).

Problem-based learning PBL offers a mode of learning which might be considered closer to real life. This real-life link is twofold: firstly, the projects or problems used often reflect or are based on real-life scenarios; secondly, the processes of team working, research, data collection, critical thinking and so on are those which will be of use to the students in their further careers. It has been suggested that learning through problem-solving may be much more effective than traditional didactic methods of learning in creating in the student's mind a body of knowledge that is useful in the future'. In PBL, students are presented with a real-life issue that requires a decision, or with a real-life problem that requires a solution. The teacher or tutor has the role of general facilitator of the group discussion, but does not direct or control the investigative process (Boud and Feletti, 1999; Kauchack and Eggen, 2007).

Project-based learning is another approach to student-centered learning based on constructivist principles. The simplest form is the well-known 'project method' used in primary and secondary schools when students work individually or collaboratively to gather and present information on a chosen topic. But projects are now becoming more ambitious and focused on real-life issues and problems that can be investigated. Project-based learning utilizes complex tasks, based on challenging questions or problems that involve students in design, problem-solving, decision making, or investigative activities, give students the opportunity to work relatively autonomously over extended periods of time, and culminate in realistic products or presentations'. The key features are that the content or focus of the study is authentic; the students are encouraged to think and reason independently, the work may involve cooperation and collaboration with others and may or may not involve the use of ICT. One of the advantages of integrating information technology into project work is that students

can learn both ICT skills and specific content knowledge simultaneously (Thomas, 2000).

Resource-based learning a methodology that allows students to learn from their own active processing of information using a range of authentic resources. Students learn effective skills for using library catalogues, making electronic searches, using CD-ROMs, making telephone calls to seek information, conducting interviews, sending and receiving emails, and writing letters. These skills are valuable for autonomous learning. RBL is suited to most areas of the school curriculum. One of its primary goals is to foster students' autonomy in learning by providing opportunities for them to work individually or collaboratively while using appropriate resources and applying relevant literacy, numeracy and study skills to explore interesting topics. In many ways, resource-based learning shares many characteristics with project-based learning (Thomas, 2000; Prosser and Trigwell, 2006).

Computer-assisted learning is method in which students are independently searching for information to complete a project or to solve a problem. Computers in the classroom have provided learners and their teachers with fast and easy ways of accessing information, communicating electronically with others. Computers and their associated software present great opportunities for motivating students, encouraging independent learning, and for improving the quality of educational programs. Findings from research into the effectiveness of CAL have generally been positive (e.g., Some studies suggest, however, that learning via a computer does not necessarily produce significantly higher achievement in students than can be produced with good quality teaching by more conventional methods. For example, a study involving more than 9000 students from the 1st, 4th and 6th grades in US schools found no significant advantage in using computer software for reading and mathematics wisely comments (Ingram and Nelson, 2008).

Across the world, information technology is dramatically altering the way students; faculty and staff learn and work. Internet-ready phones, handheld computers, digital cameras, and MP3 players are revolutionizing the college life. As the demand for technology continues to rise, colleges and universities are moving all sorts of student services, from laundry monitoring to snack delivery online. At Columbia University, a real-time Web-based service called Laundry View lets students log on to a Web-based system to see which washing machines are free before they head to the laundry room. They can monitor their wash and can even program the service to e-mail them when their load is done (Barry, 1997).

From the above, we can make out that the Information and communication technology has made many innovations in the field of teaching and also made a drastic change from the old paradigm of teaching and learning. In the new paradigm of learning, the role of

student is more important than teachers. The concepts of paperless and pen less classroom are emerging as an alternative to the old teaching learning method. Nowadays there is democratization of knowledge and the role of the teacher is changing to that of facilitator. We need to have interactive teaching and this changing role of education is inevitable with the introduction of multimedia technology and the spawning of a technologically-savvy generation of youths (Marland and Khamis, 1993).

Study Objectives

To determine student's perspective regarding teaching methodologies of community medicine department, Ayub Medical College Abbottabad.

To evaluate the teaching methodologies that are prevailing in community medicine department Ayub medical college, Abbottabad

Ethical considerations

Averbal consent was taken from all the study participants. Confidentiality and anonymity was ensured. All the Focus group and interview transcripts were kept in a locked custody of the principal researcher. The study protocol including the written consent form was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board of Research Ethics AMC, Abbottabad.

METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research seeks to understand and interpret the information about the "human" side of an issue i.e. behaviors, beliefs, opinions, emotions and relationships. We used a descriptive qualitative study design to explore and understand the perceptions of regarding the approach helped us to study the different perspectives, conflicting attitudes and experiences in relation to the research topic in-depth. The study was carried out in Ayub medical college, Abbottabad from December 2016 to August 2017. The methods primarily employed in this research were In-depth interview (IDI) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Both FDGs and Interviews were conducted among fourth year MBBS students by team mates. The sampling technique that we used in this study was non-probability purposive sampling. The questions asked to these were thoroughly discussed by the team mates and agreed upon. The students were first briefed about the procedure of FGDs and IDIs in order to make them respond fearlessly. They were ensured that the information being taken from them will be used entirely for research purpose and will remain confidential. Moreover, there was no faculty participation during the

whole data collection. Students were encouraged to provide their deepest insights. The conductor or the interviewer remained totally unbiased during the process. Each FGD comprised 6-7 student, and each in-depth interview only one participant. In all about 8 FGDs and 4 in-depth interviews were conducted. Time for each FGD and IDI was about 45 minutes. The team for conducting FGD and IDI included an anchor who has to engaged in discussion with participants and to start, propagate and finish FGD and IDI, a writer who has to write the response of participant word by word and observers whose task was to observe the response and to give feedback to other teammates about FGD and IDI. Interviews were mainly structured. Data was first recorded by audio recorder on smartphones and then transcribed by the batch mates. After completing the process of data collection, we had to analyze the data which was done manually. We took codes and sub-codes out of the data and developed categories. These categories were then enveloped in themes in order to give them a thorough meaning. After deciding themes, we briefly explained each theme in result along with the participant's comments. Finally, conclusions were drawn by comparing the result with similar studies.

RESULTS

The data collected for our study, mainly falls under these five themes.

1. Role of class environment in learning process

Class environment play a vital role in effective learning process as it is the medium through which the communication between a teacher and a student takes place. Anything wrong with this medium will led to ineffective learning. Classroom environment directly effects the students. When asked from students they complained of poor class control and inability to deliver knowledge. Many students felt reluctant to ask questions during lecture due to unfriendly response from teachers .class control is reported to be poor in some cases. Students' involvement during learning process was not encouraged usually.

Some of the common comments of our participants on role of class environment in learning process

a. Class strength and attendance strictness

"Students participate more confidently and perform better in small group". (FGD 3)

"The class strength is high, so we (students) sitting at the back can't see white board". (FGD 6)

"There should no strictness regarding attendance, and

class timings". (FGD 3)

"The class environment is not an accepting one; I go to the class just for attendance". (FGD 5)

"Our class strength is very high, that is why we can't focus on the lecture better". (IDI 2)

"Long lectures span (one hour) have bad effects on our concentration during lecture". (FGD 2)

"We (teachers) want to deliver as much better as possible. Yes, we do lock the door after 5-10mins because we want to make the students feel a sense of responsibility and punctuality which is very important for them in their professional life. We do agree that the class strength is high which shouldn't be so. The administration should make some arrangements to divide the class into 4-5 small groups this will help both the students and teacher to communicate better". (IDI 4)

"If there should be no strictness on attendance most of the students will not attend majority of the classes then how can we expect the student have learned without attending any class". (IDI 1)

b. Competition, reward and teacher's authority in class

"There is no competition among students in our class". (FGD 2)

"I think teachers have no interest to deliver, they just come and run their lecture on power point and think that they have done their job, a teacher has much more than only taking lectures". (FGD 7)

"As teacher has got the authority he/she must make sure an interactive and rewarding class environment rather than a tense and passive one-sided approach". (FGD 5)

"When we answer any question wrong the other colleagues as well as the teacher laugh which is one of the main reason student don't participate and interact actively during class". (IDI 2)

"There should be a complete rewarding environment in the class whether a student answer wrong he/she shouldn't be discouraged, so that he/she keeps involving in active learning". (FGD 1)

c. Source of disturbance in class

"When the strength of the class is high, disturbance is inevitable". (FGD 2)

"Student entering the class lately cause disturbing". (FGD 8)

"Talks among students disturb the whole class, specially the back benchers". (FGD 4)

"Power cuts (load shedding) also creates disturbance during lectures". (FGD 3)

"Circulation of attendance sheet is also a source of disturbance". (FGD 5)

2. Role of teacher in learning process

Teacher is an important stakeholder in a learning process. Teacher play a vital role in effective learning and effects the student's behavior directly. When asked from the participants of our study they commented that teacher lack the knowledge to properly use the modern technological gadgets. Many students stated that alongside lack of experience the teachers don't prepare well before delivering lecture. Some students felt reluctant to ask questions due to the strict nature of some teachers.

Some the comments that students commented during the focus group discussion on the role of teacher in learning process are given as follow.

Management skills of a teacher

"Overall management skills of the teachers are good. They do manage class environment and timings very well". (FGD 3)

"I think our teachers lack the ability to manage the class and lecture timings. They have to talk for an hour no matter what the students have learned or not". (IDI 2)

"Yes, its true most of the teacher try to involve as many students as possible, but the student's participation in this part of learning is lacking and I think we have to look at this issue from various angles". (FGD 2)
(IDI 3).

a. Academic skills of a teacher

"Teacher should be very well in the concern subject. We have just 2-3 teachers who are well experienced, other are at the level of lecturer so this how the subject seems a bit difficult". (FGD 8)

"Our teachers are well experienced but the problem is the way some teachers are teaching, they use PowerPoint which is a very passive sort of teaching that's why student don't take interest. Sir dr A teaching method is very impressive, he keeps the class interactive and student actively participate". (FGD 2)

"Teacher should understand that every student has got different mental caliber so the teacher should adopt such a method of teaching that is understandable to all". (FGD 4)

"Communication between a teacher and a student is important so teacher should have the willingness to communicate with the students well. Some of our teachers don't consider students anything". (FGD 5)

"It is not possible for a teacher to understand the psyche of the whole class (250 strength). "The department is well aware but this is some administrative issue". (IDI 1)

b. Personality of a teacher

“A teacher personality very effects the student’s behavior and learning”. (FGD 2)

“when I face a strict teacher, I don’t answer any question even if I know the right answer”. (FGD 6)

“Many students in our class remains quite because of the strictness the teachers observed, which is why most of the student lack self-confidence and active participation”. (FGD 7)

“Teachers should dress well, and he/she should be familiar with the student psyche”

“I attend classes just for the sake of attendance”. (IDI 2)

“A think a teacher is a person who compels you to think, or I would rather say a teacher should be innovative”. (FGD 2)

“The teachers of this department are well experienced, innovative and cooperative but there are certain misconceptions that teachers of this department are very strict, don’t dare to ask any question, they will give you supply, be obedient. I have been to my teachers in this department they are very cooperative I do asked questions and their response is highly appreciable”. (IDI 2)

“Attendance should be compulsory and environment should be strict “. (FGD 4)

3. Community medicine as a subject

Community medicine is an important subject in field of medicine. It deals with community and deliver knowledge on disease prevention, epidemic control and research methodology. The participants of our study have mixed sort views on this subject. Many study labelled community medicine as a tough and unimportant subject. They stated this subject is not going to help in their professional career at all that is why student do not take interest in this subject. They also stated that community medicine is very important with argument that prevention of a disease is more important than cure and the research methodology that is key for more and more innovations in medicine.

Following the verbal statements of our participants on community medicine as a subject

“Community medicine is an unimportant subject. Doctors have to treat the disease; prevention is the concern of public health department”. (FGD 6)

“I think one can have a good professional career in this subject because of the overwhelming burden of communicable diseases in today’s congested society”. (FGD 3)

“The research part of the subject should be thought to the students only; the other things are not that much important’. (FGD 8)

“It is a boring subject. I am least interested and I think it shouldn’t be a part of medicine. It should be studied

separately”. (FGD 4)

“Community Medicine is important subject. The lab reports that doctors use to confirm diagnosis of a disease, it is this subject which has provided the research for the normal range values. It is just a minor example if we seriously think about this subject it is as much important as other subjects in medicine”. (FGD 7)

4. Role of different teaching methodologies in a learning process

Teaching strategies are the principles and methods that are instrumented by teachers to attain the required optimal learning by students, which depends not only on the subject that is supposed to be taught but also by the nature and psychology of learner. The appropriation and efficiency of a teaching method lies in its relation with the characteristics of learner and the main goal it has supposed to bring about.

The most commonly used teaching methods in community medicine department is the PowerPoint teaching, lecturing by chalk and talk, field visits and small group discussions on student’s research projects. Most of the students commented that small group discussion is the best way of teaching in which every student gets the opportunity to participate. Some student did comment in favor of field visits and found it very interesting, but the lack of supervisor interest and knowledge about the visit have made some students to labeled this method useless.

Upon asking which teaching method is effective many of the students stated in favor of student centered methods. Students were of the view that those teachers who involve students interactively are more effective than those who just delivered his one-hour lecture and leave the class without knowing whether students have learned something or not. The PowerPoint that is very important tool in teaching has not been used effectively due to lack of knowledge and the purpose for which PowerPoint has been introduced.

Following are the student response on the role of various teaching methods in learning process.

“Lecture by chalk and talk is one-way method “. (FGD 5)

“PowerPoint method is commonly used, I dislike this method because it’s a one-way sort of teaching, one has to listen to teacher for an hour and all in vane”. (FGD 3)

“Mostly the teachers don’t involve the students, they just deliver their lecture and mark our attendance and leave the class”. (FGD 6)

“Field visits are very interesting in which you learn thing practically on grounds”. (FGD 8)

“Every method is equally good it depends on a teacher how he delivers his lecture”. (FGD 1)

“Note book writing is waste of time; prewritten notes

should be given to the students and should be evaluated accordingly". (FGD 4)

"Interactive sessions like weekly discussions on research projects students are highly effective, but it is limited due to resources and administrative issues". (FGD 5)

"Fields visits are very effective if we can increase the time and circle of visits so that students get more and more interest in learning in subject". (IDI 1)

"Class strength affects the teacher's teaching method and student learning process. Students sitting at the back complain of being uninvolved in learning and interaction in the class which results in disturbance in the class". (FGD 3)

"Class strength does matter but it's up to the teacher how well he manages his class. Some teachers are so good in managing class that all the students fully observed attention and take interest". (FGD 8)

5. Evaluation methods in community medicine department and its effectiveness

The commonly used evaluation methods that are implied in community medicine department are the objectively structured practical examinations (OSPE) and unit wise written exam as well as internal oral viva. Upon asking about the evaluation methods and their effectiveness, students expressed their satisfaction over these methods and stated that yes, these methods are well enough to evaluate the students properly. While other students are of the view that community medicine is a strict department, there is no criteria for fail and pass. They said that the internal assessment and attendance all what you need to pass the subject in annual exam. Some students also complain that there is a sort of inequality in the evaluation methods of the department. Some batches have easy OSPE and viva other have so different OSPE that even toppers cannot pass. Some student also stated that the department favor female in annual exam.

The response that student recorded when asked about the evaluation methods in community medicine department in their own verbatim is given as follow.

"The evaluation methods are okay, but the thing is that students don't study on time that's why they face problems when they appear in stages or OSPE". (FGD 2)

"There is inequality in internal OPSE and viva, those students who have ward in the start of session have not studied the book so when ask in viva they are completely blank while those who have their wards in the middle or in last of session they have studied well so they go through the viva and OSPE easily". (FGD 3)

"If you have good attendance no matter if stages are failed you will pass in annual exam". (FGD 1)

"No matter what if you did well in annual but your attendance is short and your stages are failed, you will not pass annual exam". (FGD 8)

"Schedule of internal evaluation tests should be notified at the start of session, so that the student starts studying from the beginning". (FGD 5)

"Internal assessment should not be given that much weightage". (FGD 2)

"Attendance strictness by department shouldn't be observed, we all have to study ourselves to pass in annual exam". (FGD 7)

"Timings of the classes should be properly managed as classes are usually missed due to field visits". (FGD 6)

6. Administrative issues that pinged hurdles in the way of effective learning environment, teaching methodologies and evaluation methods

Teaching is a multidimensional task. It is not only the teacher who is wholly responsible for the proper provision of effective teaching method. Administrative issues like resources, materials and proper system for teachers training are also required for an optimally effective learning process. The participants in our study mostly complained off the class strength and stated that the class strength has greatly effected there learning. There is no scheme for the training and workshops of teachers. The curriculum and timetable that have raised questions among masses should also be considered by the administration. There also complained about the compulsion of attendance.

Important comments of participants on role of administration in effective teaching are as:

a. Teaching seminars and workshops

"Yes, teachers training seminars are very important; the teachers are able to adopt new ways of teaching skills". (FGD 7)

"Teachers don't attend any seminar for their training". (FGD 5)

"The government should arrange some national and international teachers exchange visits so that our teachers get familiar with the modern techs used in teaching". (FGD 3)

DISCUSSION

Medical education is playing a key role in the progress of any country. Across the world increasing attention is being given to the advancement and improvement in medical studies and its methods of teaching. So, there is the need to adopt the proper methods, incorporates the advance technologies to fully equip the doctor with functional tools and make him ready for his purpose (Rehman et al., 2012). For making the learning process more efficient, we had undergone a study to know the

student's perception about different methods of teaching in our college, the area in which improvements may be made and to know which method they find most appropriate for the effective and long-term learning.

Participants of all FGDs in our study preferred the small group discussion. They were of the view that it is a two-way transfer of knowledge and it focuses on the students, allow the students to interact with their teachers and enhances their problem-solving capacity, which in turn results in the long-term learning and imparts quality knowledge. In small group discussion students get opportunity to actively participate, discuss their own problems and try to solve them. This not only builds up their confidence and increase their motivation but also improves their self-directed learning skills and communication skills. Students from all over the world preferred small group discussion ahead of other methods of learning (Habib et al., 2006).

The modern method of teaching has modified the role of teacher as a facilitator, which is not acceptable for some of the teachers as they think this will result in loss of control of their process (Miller et al., 2013). Teachers, who were interviewed, considered small group discussion as the problem solving approach and the way of imparting the long-term knowledge and learning. However, at the same time, they stated that the entire course cannot be covered by this method, for a fruitful small group discussion, we need specific faculty members, group of people for discussion, learning environment and multimedia aid for the better learning process (Shaguptha, 2015; Priyadarshini et al., 2012).

The study of previous scholars stand by results of our work that small group discussion is an effective way of better learning. Different studies carried out at different time's show that both the students and teacher prefers the combination of lectures and problem based learning, because it increases the students interest, enhance their problem-solving capacity and helps to improve the decision-making skills of students. A study conducted at Dove Medical College has shown that problem based learning helps the medical students to understand the basic concepts, increase their knowledge, improve communication skills and help them to enhance the process of self-learning (Sewasew et al., 2015).

The knowledge and expertise of the topic by the lecturer has also been an attraction of the students towards the class. It has positive impact, because the students think that they can get the beneficial knowledge from the expert of the field. Other attracting factors can be the attitude of the lecturer towards the class, how regularly teacher takes the class and how positively he interacts with his student. The self-behavior of teacher has the influencing effect on students to attract them towards the class (Ansari, 2017). The data analysis shows a huge different between the students who attends the class and those who do not attend. Attending the lectures helps the students to increase their span of

attention and make them active in the class. The main reason behind not attending the lecture is not finding it attractive. Marking attendance is one of major driving tool of students towards class and lectures. The study shows that 74% of students are attracted toward class due to strict attendance rules of teachers (Thakur et al., 2016).

The way that the lecture is delivered should provoke the interest of the students. In our study student considered the white board method of lecture ahead of multimedia presentations. White board and talkative method is the traditional and is somehow natural in the sense teachers pass additional information than pre-planned lecture, meanwhile it gives student time to take the notes which will help them later. This method provides more interaction between teachers and students, which makes it more effective than multimedia aided presentations, which focus on certain points and less interactive (Hay et al., 2005).

In PowerPoint method of presentation teacher just deliver the prepared lectures and skips the important information. Students of four FGDs were of the view that teachers take the prepared slides from net and just go through the slide, which results the loss of attraction in the lectures. Mostly teachers take the power Point as the fast way of delivering the lectures and tries to cover the course as soon as possible which in turns cause the hassle and loss of attention towards lectures which effect the learning process. The studies show that advancement in technology not necessarily increases the interest of student; on the other hand, sometime traditional methods are more effective (Majeed, 2016).

A sea change in the mindset of instructors and students is required to remove the outdated methods of teaching subjects. Most often, teachers adopt a monotonous style of imparting wisdom to the students and do little to make these subjects intellectually stimulating and engaging. As a result, students begin to lose their interest and are reluctant to study subjects (Ansari, 2017).

It has also been found from most of the students that conventional lecture approach in classroom is of limited effectiveness in both teaching and learning. In such type of learning approach, students assume a purely passive role and their attention fades off after 20 to 30 minutes. So, it is intensely need of the hour that the teachers must prioritize and adopt methods which favor students and encourage them to learn. Teaching improvement for teacher is as much necessary as optimal qualification and pertinent experience of subjects (Majeed, 2016).

Teaching improvements in higher education in general have been slow in coming. Tradition has maintained date if a person has attained the doctorate in a given field, he is capable of teaching. This new development is helping in educating faculties more and more. They must not rely on outdated strategies and focus on providing a holistic approach to the subjects.

Training sessions are also frequent assessment and helpful technique for teachers to achieve improvements in teaching. The teacher needs to take a few steps to encourage students by providing friendly classroom environment, reduction in communication gap, and assessing of student psychology to develop intellectual curiosity in students regarding the subject. These practices will serve the dual purpose of building the aptitude of students and fostering an interest in subjects which are otherwise considered to be dull (Roush and Holcomb, 2001).

Lectures convey the knowledge to a large community in limited possible resources and are the most commonly tools used in the studies. Mostly students do not considered lectures as an attractive way of learning. The way of delivering lecture of a lecturer has a huge impact on imparting the knowledge. The study of Miller and McNeal shows that the teacher who engages the students in the lecture has a better impact on the grades. Pre-class lecture imparts a better impact on students learning, because it improves the teacher student interaction which is the key point of better learning (Teaching methods, 2017). Dobson used an online questionnaire to make the student's interaction with the topic and enhance interactive learning. Marking attendance is one of major driving tool of students towards class and lectures. The study shows that 74% of students are attracted toward class due to strict attendance rules of teachers (Majumdar et al., 2015).

The way how the lecture is delivered should provoke the interest of the students. In our study student considered the white board method of lecture ahead of multimedia presentations. White board and talkative method is the traditional and is somehow natural in the sense teachers pass additional information than pre-planned lecture, meanwhile it gives student time to take the notes which will help them later. This method provides more interaction between teachers and students which makes it more effective than multimedia aided presentations which focus on certain points and less interactive (Thakur et al., 2016). In PowerPoint method of presentation teacher just deliver the prepared lectures and skips the important information. Most of students think that teachers take the prepared slides from net and just go through the slide which results the loss of attraction in the lectures. Mostly teachers take the power Point as the fast way of delivering the lectures and tries to cover the course as soon as possible which in turns cause the hassle and loss of attention towards lectures which effect the learning process. The studies show that advancement in technology not necessarily increases the interest of student; on the other hand, sometime traditional methods are more effective (Roush and Holcomb, ND).

Community medicine as defined by WHO, "The study of health and disease in the population of defined communities or group in order to identify their health

needs, and to plan, implement and evaluate health programs to effectively meet these needs". It is different from other medical subjects as it is mostly concerned with disease prevention and health promotion by doing research based study and by directly interacting with whole community. It is a backbone of all the clinical aspect of medical sciences.

Medical students often take community medicine as a tough and boring subject. Being turned over the years to anatomical, physiological and pathological configurations, and as they are more enthusiastic to experience the joy of palpatory and auscultatory skills, community medicine takes them away from the sweet dreams of being a doctor in air-conditioned comfort, little does they realize that community medicine offers them the only link with real life experience and enables them to see a system of health care which is most relevant to the need of our community.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is that teaching is a multidimensional process, which involves key stakeholders that are the teachers, students, and the administration. For an effective teaching, all the stakeholders must work optimally. On teaching methods based on results, the participants were unsatisfied and labeled these current methods as ineffective. But if we look at the situation this is an administrative issue which has to create a productive learning environment by dividing the class of such huge rolls into small groups and make sure the availability of faculty staff for them. The strictness of attendance is another issue many participants referred to but if we look at this attendance should not be a big deal. If there is an environment where student can learn effectively they will probably attend classes not because these are mandatory but to learn something. Teacher's training seminars, which have to be regularly conducted, are lacking. This is the duty of administration to device a system of training for teachers. Behavior of students also affects a learning process; students have to be teaching the ethics, punctuality and the sense of professionalism from the very beginning so that their behavior ensures a creative learning environment. The evaluation methods should be revisit whether these tools are effective or not. Because the participants of our study showed a vague response which shows some shortcomings

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